

SOME PROBLEMS OF IMPROVING WRITTEN SPEECH SKILLS IN CONDITIONS OF DIGITALIZATION

Assistant professor Alimov F.

ASU, Uzbekistan.

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The relevance of the research in conditions of digitalization is related to the need for integration into the world community and the achievement of intercultural communication in a contradictory world environment.

The aim of the research in conditions of digitalization is the theoretical substantiation, development and experimental proof of the effectiveness of the methodological system for the formation of students' writing skills in the context of digitalization of the educational space of the university. The object of the research in conditions of digitalization is the process of forming the skills of communicatively directed written speech of Uzbek students in the context of digitalization of the educational process of non-philological faculties of the university. The subject of the research in conditions of digitalization is a methodological system for the formation of writing skills of Uzbek students in the context of digitalization in teaching English.

Research objectives: 1. To reveal the theoretical, methodological and methodological foundations for the formation of students' writing skills in the educational space of the university. 2. To develop a model for the stage-by-stage formation of writing skills of university students using a differentiated approach to the technique of writing and writing in the context of digitalization of education. 3. To identify on a scientific basis the semantic-syntactic and grammatical difficulties of students' written communication based on a comparative analysis of the means of expression in writing and written speech in English and Uzbek. 4. To develop a system of exercises for the formation of writing skills in the context of digitalization of students of non-philological faculties and identify innovative digital methodological tools. 5. To identify the methodological conditions for the formation of writing skills of Uzbek students and experimentally test the effectiveness of the developed methodological system in the context of digitalization of the educational space of the university.

Research methods. To achieve the goals of the study and solve the tasks set in it, the methods of analysis of linguistic, didactic and psychological and methodological literature, pedagogical observation, comparative analysis, experiment, pedagogical monitoring, questioning, experimental method, processing of the experimental results were used. Experimental base of the research is conducted on the basis of Andijan State University (Uzbekistan). The results of the research in conditions of digitalization are as follows: 1. The theoretical, methodological and methodological foundations for the formation of students' writing skills in the educational space of the university have been supplemented and concretized. 2. A model has been developed for the stage-by-stage formation of writing skills of university students using a differentiated approach to the technique of writing and written speech in the context of digitalization of education. 3. The semantic-syntactic and grammatical difficulties of written communication of students were identified on a scientific basis on the basis of a comparative analysis of the means of expression in writing and written speech in English and Uzbek. 4. A system of exercises for the formation of writing skills in the context

of digitalization of students of non-philological faculties has been developed and innovative digital methodological tools have been identified. 5. The methodological conditions for the formation of writing skills of Uzbek students in the context of digitalization of the educational space of the university are identified, namely: to determine the methodological characteristics of the system for the formation of students' writing skills in the context of digitalization based on a differentiated approach to writing and written speech, as well as the organization of independent work and assessment of students; to develop methodological tools for the formation of writing skills among students, taking into account its psychological and linguistic characteristics in the context of digitalization of the educational space of the university; to provide ways and methods of teaching written communication of Uzbek students, taking into account the written and speech peculiarities of the language units of the native language, taking into account the semantic-syntactic and grammatical structure of the text; to determine the writing technique of Uzbek students of non-philological faculties on the basis of identifying the formation of their phonetic, grammatical and lexical skills in the context of digitalization of the educational space of the university; to develop a methodological model for the formation of writing skills of Uzbek students based on comparative, project-research, interactive, research-oriented methods in the absence of a language environment.

The theoretical significance lies in the creation and scientific justification of the theoretical and methodological foundations for developing a methodology for teaching written speech to Uzbek students in the context of digitalization of the educational space of the university. The revealed differential factors of writing and written speech as a result of a comparative analysis of the English and Uzbek languages can improve the theory and methodology of teaching communicative-oriented written speech of Uzbek students in the absence of a language environment.

The practical significance of the research in conditions of digitalization is determined by the development of methodological tools, in general, and a system of tasks and exercises, in particular, which can be used to form the writing skills of university students in the context of digitalization of education. The results of the research in conditions of digitalization can be used by methodologists when creating textbooks, teaching aids, by students when writing final qualification works and master's theses, to develop a program for the practice of oral and written speech in teaching English, as well as within the framework of the basic course of foreign language teaching methods for language students at the university. Therefore, the results of the research in conditions of digitalization together contain a significant scientific basis for the development of a methodological system for the formation of writing skills among Uzbek students in the context of digitalization. The identified effective factors in the formation of writing skills of Uzbek students in the context of digitalization at the methodological and psychological-linguistic levels can positively influence the development of the theory and methodology of teaching English.

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